

Pulse crop residue as N source in rice-based cropping system

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Incorporating green leaf manures to maintain soil fertility and to

Table 1. Effect of incorporating pulse residues on succeeding rice crop yields. Coimbatore, India.^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Green gram stalks incorporated + 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha	4.4	7.4
Green gram stalks incorporated + no fertilizer	3.2	4.7
Green gram stalks cut + 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha	3.8	6.4
Green gram stalks cut + no fertilizer	2.9	4.1
Soybean stalks incorporated + 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha	4.4	8.1
Soybean stalks incorporated + no fertilizer	3.8	5.9
Soybean stalks cut + 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha	4.3	6.9
Soybean stalks cut + no fertilizer	3.3	4.2

^aData not statistically analyzed.

economize on fertilizer costs has been a farmer practice. But because costs of collecting and transporting have become major hurdles, the practice is being discontinued. An integrated system of pulses grown for both grain and green manure would help reduce costs and maintain soil fertility.

We compared residual N from two pulse crops — green gram Co 4 and soybean Co 1 — grown with normal fertilization in Jun-Aug preceding a Sep-Jan rice crop. Experimental field soil at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University was clay loam with pH 7.9, low available N, medium available P, and high available K. The rice variety

was Co 43 (135 d). Plot size was 130 m².

Treatments were pulse crop residues incorporated after harvest, with and without recommended 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha. The trial was not replicated because it studied residual effects of pulse crop residues on rice yield in large plots.

Soybean stalks added more residue than green gram did (Table 1). Chemical analysis showed that soybean residue added 52 kg N/ha and green gram residues, 43 kg N/ha.

Returns were highest when soybean stalks were incorporated without fertilizer application to rice (Table 2). □

Table 2. Economic return of pulse crop residue incorporated preceding rice. Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Total return (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Return/\$ invested
Green gram stalks incorporated + 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha	780	475	2.56
Green gram stalks incorporated + no fertilizer	553	316	2.33
Green gram stalks cut + 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha	625	370	2.21
Green gram stalks cut + no fertilizer	510	275	2.15
Soybean stalks incorporated + 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha	798	493	2.61
Soybean stalks incorporated + no fertilizer	664	426	2.80
Soybean stalks cut + 100-22-42 kg NPK/ha	760	454	2.49
Soybean stalks cut + no fertilizer	562	328	2.38

Fertilizer efficiency with dry placement

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We studied the relative efficiency of fertilizer incorporated in dry soil and in puddled soil. Experimental soil was heavy-textured clay loam, pH 8.0. In both treatments, 26 kg P/ha was basally applied. IR6 was the test variety.

In dry soil incorporation, the soil was well pulverized and 80 kg N/ha placed in deep furrows. Irrigation water was applied immediately after leveling. Leveling was repeated twice in standing water before transplanting. In puddled soil incorporation, the field was flooded 20 d before transplanting

Productive tillers, weed count, yield and water use under different fertilizer placement methods.^a Sadhoke (Sheikhupura), Pakistan.

Fertilizer placement	Weed count 30 DT ^b (no./m ²)	Productive tillers/plant (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Water use ^c (mm)	Fertilizer efficiency (kg yield/kg N)	Water use efficiency (kg/mm per ha)
Puddled soil (no fertilizer)	4	9 b	4.6 c	1575	—	2.9
Incorporation of fertilizer in dry soil	5	15 a	8.0 a	1725	34	4.6
Incorporation of fertilizer in puddled soil	4	14 a	7.2 b	1950	26	3.7

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b Days after transplanting. ^c Excluding rainfall.

and conventionally puddled with 80 kg N/ha applied before the last plowing and leveling. At panicle initiation, 20 kg N/ha was applied to both treatments.

There was no significant difference in number of productive tillers

between treatments (see table). However, yield was significantly higher with fertilizer incorporated in dry soil. Weed count was slightly higher in dry soil. However, dry soil incorporation used more water. □